

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK INTERROGATIVE PRONOUNS FOR LINGUA DIDACTIC PURPOSES

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to reveal peculiarities and characteristics of interrogative pronouns in Uzbek and English which belong to different language families. Similarities and differences of interrogative pronouns in both languages are shown as a primary factor in current article. Furthermore, its significance and usage for different purposes, especially, didactic and linguistic spheres are analyzed in detail.

Nowadays most problematic issues is applied to typological classification of various languages which belong to different language families. According to the genealogical classification of world languages English belong to Indo-European language family while Uzbek is Turkish family. The term Indo-European language is used to refer to that huge language family which includes a number of languages from Asia and Europe. This language family is divided in to a number of branches which themselves include many languages. Nevertheless, There are an array of similarities between them according to grammatical and morphological language levels. We try to prove it through the examples of Interrogative Pronouns.

Introgative pronouns in both languages are utilized in order to make questions which require full answer instead of short answer "yes or no ". Besides that they are dedicated to find particular parts of speech in Uzbek and English. We illustrate it through following sentences:

Who- kim ? is focused on asking about person who is subject of sentence.

Who saw Tom ? Or Kim bu ishni qildi.

What-nima ? Also applies to ask object or thing which serves as a subject and Object in sentence.

What is your name? Or bu nima? Here its function is a subject but,

What did you do yesterday? Or Nimani bilasan ? In these sentences they are object.

Which -qaysi ? Asks about words which serves as determination in sentences through adjectives and possessive pronouns. They can come with nouns or without them:

Which is your car? Or Sening do'sting qaysi? Which book is theirs? Or qaysi faslni yoqtirasan?

When -Qachon? Asks time and the words which can be respond for them, serve as modify of time in sentences.

When did you buy this car? or Qachon kelasan?

Where -qayer demand to reply to places which can be modify of places.

Where do you live? Or qayerda o'qiysan?

Why -Nima uchun ? Asks reasons for action or situations.

Why didn't you come to the lesson? or Nega bunday qilding?

How -qanday ? is used to ask the sign of action and an the answer is expressed by adverbs.

How do they play music? or ular qanday yugurdi?

How many -qancha, nechta? is focused on finding the number of person or thing for countable nouns.

How many people are there? or qancha kitobing bor? But we apply to another structure or word to express questions for uncountable nouns in English while in uzbek there is not the notion about countable and uncountable nouns. Thus, in uzbek the same word, Qancha is only utilized to formulate question.

Besides that, these interrogative pronouns serve as a conjunction which enables to connect two simple sentences which fulfill each other through adding extra information about person, thing and place. For instance:

Who is used to form one complex sentence through connecting two simple ones on subject or object.

I know a man. The man always wears a black suit.

I know a man who always wears a black suit.

Which is utilized for things, objects, animals:

She bought a new phone. This phone was expensive.

She bought a new phone which was expensive.

Where gives chance to connect sentences related to places.

They live in Tashkent. Tashkent is the capital of Uzbekistan.

They live in Tashkentt where is the capital of Uzbekistan.

In uzbek this kind of structure is also exist. But, interrogative pronouns do not form question. For example:

Kimki yaxshi o'qiysa, o'sha imtixonidan o'tadi.

Nimani orzu qilsang, o'shanga erishasan.

All above mentioned are similarities of interrogative pronouns in uzbek and English while it is obvious to notice several distinctive features. First of all, In uzbek there are 3 types of questions forms and two of them are formed by interrogative pronouns. They are : special and tag " ritorik" question, which does not require exact answer and it has the reply in itself. They are pronounced with emotion in raised tone. For instance:

Men nechun seaman O'zbekistonni?

Onani kim sevmaydi?

Aslida dunyoda tanho nima bor ?

But in English this kind of questions are formed without interrogative pronouns. Instead of it word order help to create a question which consists of two parts. First part of sentence is

positive and the second one is question but it looks like the first one. Moreover, if first part becomes positive the second part should be negative.

The weather is hot, is not it ?

They are learning English, are not they?

He does not know English, does he?

You can not run fast, can you?

To sum up interrogative pronouns have an array of similarities and differences in Uzbek and English which they are applied not only to express human surprise and interest but also to ask special questions which replies full answers.

References:

1. <https://moluch.ru/archive/112/28159/> (дата обращения: 12.03.2023).
2. Kasymova N.F (2011) "Asymmetry in translation of interrogative sentences with questionword 'WHAT' (based on the English, Russian and Uzbek languages). Bulletin of theChelyabinsk State University.№ 11 (226)